

NDAC/LO/046

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Step 2/3 Formation and Solution of Normal Equations (WP6240, 6260, 6270)

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1. Introduction

This note is an intermediate status report on the development of two major programs in Step 2/3, respectively for the setting up (accumulation) and solution of normal equations. The intention is to have, early in 1985, a fully usable software package for these purposes, albeit with rather primitive interfaces and input/output routines. Upgrading of the latter and other adaptations to the software environment at DSRI is foreseen as a later task.

I will assume that 'observations', that is abscissae from Step 1, are available in strict order of object identification number (ID). A separate software package, under development by S Söderhjem, will effect the sorting of the chronological (set-wise) abscissa determinations into this required form (WP6230).

2. Main Programs

There are two main programs, namely

ACCU23 - accumulation of normals with simultaneous elimination (preadjustment) of astrometric parameters;

SOLV23 - pseudo-solution of normals with updating of set zero points and global parameters.

Since the overall adjustment procedure is iterative, the two programs are run in an alternating sequence: ACCU23, SOLV23, ACCU23, SOLV23, ... No automatic control is foreseen for this procedure.

ACCU23 can be run in two different modes: 'initial mode' and 'update mode'. In 'initial mode', the normals are set up from scratch, defining the unknowns to be included and criteria for selecting PRS stars; in 'update mode', however, only the right-hand side (rhs) of the normals is calculated. The purpose of this latter mode is to save computing time, by avoiding the time-consuming calculation and Cholesky reduction of the matrix (left-hand side). In update mode the selection of unknowns and PRS stars must of course be exactly the same as for the previous initial

mode run; this is guaranteed by saving various tables of unknowns and other parameters for the block structure of the normals, and by noting the weight of each object in the PRS solution.

In a sense, also SOLV23 is run either in 'initial' or 'update' mode, in that the Cholesky reduction of the matrix is automatically skipped if the matrix is already reduced. This is part of a more general provision to cope with interruptions of the solution program, whether intentional or not. (The solution may take several days.) The normals are stored in some 100-150 blocks (records) of equal length (some 15,000-20,000 double-precision reals), and the first number in each block is a status parameter, telling how far the accumulation and solution programs have processed the block. Restarting either program after some interruption, the status of each block is inspected by the program and the process resumed at the correct point.

The logical structures of the two programs are described in separate sections below.

3. Files

All input/output data handling is made directly through standard FORTRAN 77 routines, with ensuing restrictions as to the type and organization of records. Fixed unit numbers are assigned by a PARAMETER statement in the INCLUDE-segment which is part of all program units. The files are usually unformatted, with the exception of the starting file STARTF and the log file. STARTF is furthermore the only filename defined by the programs; other filenames can be chosen freely by the operator and are given in STARTF. The following gives a short description of each file.

STARTF

(Sequential access, formatted, UNIT=11, READ only)

This contains filenames for the other files and defines the unknowns to be used in the solution:

- the number of astrometric parameters per star (NSAPAR = 2, 3, or 5);
- the selection of global parameters to include (from a menu of up to 128 predefined parameters);
- the set numbers (j) to include. These are defined by intervals (j1 to j2, plus j3 to j4, ...) instead of enumeration.

STARTF also contains a 'run number', which should in principle be changed each time any of the input files have been changed. The purpose of this number is to have a simple way for the programs to know, if this is a new

run, or just a continuation of an old one.

Object Catalogue (ca 16 Mb)

(Direct access, unformatted, UNIT=12, READ and WRITE.)

This contains one record of 20 d.p. reals (160 bytes) per object, viz. the array OPAR(1:20) introduced in NDAC/LO/044.

RGC Catalogue (ca 0.08 Mb)

(Direct access, unformatted, UNIT=13, READ and WRITE.)

This contains one record of 34 bytes per set (RGC), viz. j , α_{rj} , δ_{rj} , c_j , T_j .

Global parameters (1 kb)

(Direct access, unformatted, UNIT=14, READ and WRITE.)

This contains a single record of 128 d.p. reals, which are initially set to $\emptyset\emptyset$ and updated by SOLV23.

Blocking data (0.03 Mb)

(Sequential access, unformatted, UNIT=15, READ and WRITE.)

This contains general information on the block structure of the normals, as well as tables of the unknowns included, run number, etc.

Normals (ca 16 Mb)

(Direct access, unformatted, UNIT=16, READ and WRITE.)

This contains the blocked normals, with the right-hand side in a separate block. The first number (d.p. real) of each block (record) is a status parameter.

Observations (60 Mb)

(Sequential access, unformatted, UNIT=17, READ only.)

This contains one (variable-length) record per observed object, viz.:

ID, NOBS, (j, ABSC, SDABSC)

where the list in () is repeated NOBS times. Only ABSC (observed abscissa) is d.p. (REAL*8), other items are INTEGER*4 and REAL*4. The record are assumed to be ordered for strictly increasing ID. NOTE: It is not necessary that the whole file is available in a single run; the accumulation by ACCU23 may be interrupted when there are no more observations in the disk file, and resumed when a new batch of observations has been stored on the disk.

Asylum (of the order of 20 Mb)

(Sequential access, unformatted, UNIT=18, WRITE only.)

This contains one (variable-length) record per star, for which no reasonable solution was found with the single star model. The contents are (TBR):

ID, OPAR(1:20), NOBS, (j, ABSC, SDABSC, ACOEFF(1:NASPAR), RES3)

This includes all the 'astrometric' information needed for subsequent double-star analysis, to be complemented by 'photometric' information from the IDT signal catalogue. The size 20 Mb corresponds to a fraction of 13% of the stars falling in this category. Data for a specific object can also be directed to this file by means of the IPRS function (see below).

Log

(Sequential access, formatted, UNIT=19, WRITE only.)

Milestones of the processing are logged on this file in a standard format: date, time, message (40 char) [, integer]

Typical milestones may be: start/stop of execution, processing of every n:th object by ACCU23, completed reduction of a block by SOLV23. The log can of course be inspected by the operator during a run, without interfering with the program. The file cannot be overwritten by the programs, i.e. all additions are made at the end of the existing file.

4. Block structure of normals

The columnwise storage of normals used by ACCU23 and SOLV23 is similar to the scheme used at Geodetic Institute (Charlottenlund). The arrangement is primarily determined by the adopted solution method — the Cholesky algorithm operating on at most two columns at a time. The algorithm has two parts, which I shall refer to as the 'Cholesky reduction' (formally, pre-multiplication by the inverse of the square-root of the symmetric matrix; this is applied to the matrix itself as well as to the rhs) and the 'Cholesky back-substitution' (formally the solution of the triangular system consisting of column 1 to n, where $n = ncol, ncol-1, \dots$, of the Cholesky reduced equations). The two parts are approximately described by the following double loops:

Cholesky reduction:

```

for i = 1 to ncol
  for j = 1 to i
    columni := f(columni, columnj)
  next j
next i

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Cholesky back-substitution:

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for i = ncol to 2 step -1
  for j = i-1 to 1 step -1
    columni := g(columni, columnj)
  next j
next i

```

(If only the solution, and not the whole inverse matrix is required, the second algorithm only runs through $i = ncol =$ the right-hand side.) With blockwise storage of columns, the double loops are simply replaced by two outer loops through the blocks, and two inner through the columns of the blocks. Clearly the solution program must have at most two blocks at a time in primary memory, but within this restriction it is of course advantageous to use as long blocks as possible, to minimize the number of disk accesses. A blocklength of some 15,000-20,000 d.p. reals may be suitable, and gives 100-150 blocks for a system with 2000 unknowns.

Only the upper-diagonal part of each column is stored. Furthermore, a large part of the column may be empty (contain zeroes), so that only rows IROW1(I) to I are in general stored of column I. (That is, IROW1(I) is the first non-zero row of column I.) The array IROW1(1:NCOL) defines the profile of the system. (Actually, I assume IROW1(I) = 1 for all I, i.e. a full matrix. This is more or less true of the Step 2 equations. The programs are general enough to cope with a reduced profile, if required.) Given the profile and the maximum length of a block (MXLBLK), a special subroutine calculates the block structure as defined by the following numbers:

```

NBLK      = number of blocks
LBLK      = actual length of each block ( $\leq$  MXLBLK)
ICOL1(K), ICOL2(K) = first, last column in block K
IROWØ(I)  = 'origin address' of column I, such that matrix element
           (J,I) is stored as element IROWØ(I)+J in respective
           block

```

The first number in each block is a status parameter, indicating how far the block has been processed:

<u>value</u>	<u>status of block</u>
0D0	all elements = 0D0
dbl(ID)	ID is the last object processed by ACCU23 on this block. That is, accumulation may be resumed with next object > ID
-1D0	accumulation complete, normals have been 'fixed' (made non-singular)
-2D0	block has been Cholesky reduced
-3D0	block has been Cholesky back-substituted

When the last block (containing the rhs only) has status -3, it contains the solution for the set zero points and global parameters.

Whenever ACCU23 or SOLV23 are started (except in a new 'initial' run), they automatically check the status of each block and proceed accordingly (e.g. resuming accumulation at the appropriate point of the observations file).

5. Logical structure of ACCU23

The accumulation of normals follows a scheme very similar to Table 1 in NDAC/LO/022 (definition of Back-substitution). For the general problem of setting up the blocked normals, while eliminating 'local' unknowns (the attitude in Step 1, the astrometric parameters in Step 2/3), there are essentially two different ways in which the loops can be nested:

- (i) to go through all observations separately for each block;
- (ii) to go through all blocks for each group of local parameters.

The first method minimizes the number of disk operations, while the second minimizes computations (the observation equations are only computed once). The preferred method therefore depends on the complexity of the observation equations (including the elimination of local parameters) versus disk access time. For Step 1, at least in geometrical mode, where the observation equations are very simple, the first method is probably best, while the second method should be better for Step 2/3. The scheme set up in Table 1 of NDAC/LO/022 follows (ii). The scheme adopted below includes an important modification, however. It is clearly wasteful to update the blocks after every PRS star, since the primary memory can easily accommodate the observation equations of perhaps a hundred stars at a time.

A working array $W(,)$ is therefore used to set up observation equations for as many PRS stars as possible. Only when the array cannot accommodate the next star in the observation sequence, are the normals updated. The disposition of $W(,)$ is shown in Figure 1. Each PRS star takes NOBS + NASPAR rows, namely for the observations (NOBS) and the 'local normals' of the astrometric parameters (NASPAR). After Cholesky reduction of these five equations,

$$\left(\begin{array}{c} \underline{P} \\ \underline{R} \\ \underline{s} \end{array} \right) \text{ modified to } \left(\begin{array}{c} \tilde{\underline{P}} \\ \tilde{\underline{R}} \\ \tilde{\underline{s}} \end{array} \right) = \tilde{\underline{P}}^{-T} \left(\begin{array}{c} \tilde{\underline{P}} \\ \tilde{\underline{R}} \\ \tilde{\underline{s}} \end{array} \right) \quad (1)$$

the preadjustment can be made (solving $\tilde{\underline{P}} \underline{\Delta a} = \tilde{\underline{s}}$), possibly invoking MESH to resolve slit errors. Then the row vectors $\underline{A}_{ij}$ are replaced by $\underline{H}'_{ij} = \underline{B}'_{ij} \underline{A}_{ij} \underline{P}^{-1}$ (by making the Cholesky reduction as if $\underline{A}'_{ij}$ were the rhs), whereupon the equations are in the suitable form for updating the normals.

Before all this, however, the star must pass a number of tests to be qualified as a PRS star. This is to a large part governed by the function IPRS(OPAR), which takes one of the following values depending on the status of the object in the object catalogue:

<u>IPRS value</u>	<u>Object status</u>
-2	object is to be skipped by ACCU23;
-1	object shall not be included as PRS, and no preadjustment made, but equations should be output to Asylum;
0	object shall not be included as PRS, but preadjustment should be made, if possible;
1	object shall be preadjusted and included as PRS, if possible;
2	object is to be preadjusted and included as PRS, <u>unconditionally</u> .

Status IPRS = 2 is only used in 'update mode', to guarantee that exactly the same PRS stars are used as in the previous 'initial mode' run (when a note was made in OPAR about the weight of the star in the PRS accumulation). The stars with IPRS = 1 in 'initial mode' are therefore either IPRS = 0 or 2 in a subsequent 'update mode'.

A draft scheme for the logical structure of ACCU23 is shown below.

1. Read STARTF file. If a blocking data file exists (as named in STARTF), it is read before a possible recalculation of blocking data.
2. For a new run, zero the appropriate columns (all columns in 'initial mode', rhs only in 'update mode').
3. Find the ID number of the last object treated for all blocks (by inspection of the status parameter of each block). Position observations file to the next object.
4. Read RGC and global parameters.
5. Process a batch of stars:
 - 5.1. Zero star counter (ISTAR) and pointers (IW0, IW1).
 - 5.2. Input observations for next object. If there are no more stars or not room for next star in W(,) array, go to 5.10.
 - 5.3. Input OPAR from object catalogue and compute IPRS. If (IPRS = -2), go to 5.2.
 - 5.4. Calculate observation equations. If (IPRS = -1) or (NOBS < NASPAR), go to 5.9.
 - 5.5. Attempt preadjustment of astrometric parameters. If singular, go to 5.9. If χ^2 unsatisfactory after adjustment, try MESH. If χ^2 still unsatisfactory, and (IPRS $\neq$ 2), then go to 5.9.
 - 5.6. If (IPRS $\neq$ 0), go to 5.2.
 - 5.7. At this point the star is finally accepted as PRS star. If (IPRS $\neq$ 2), then make a note of the run number and weight in OPAR. Update star counter and pointers for W(,) array, and modify W(,) as required ($\underline{A}_{ij} \rightarrow \tilde{\underline{H}}_{ij}$, $\underline{R} \rightarrow \tilde{\underline{R}}$, etc).
 - 5.8. Go to 5.2.
 - 5.9. Output OPAR and observation equations (except for globals) to asylum. Go to 5.2.
 - 5.10. Update normals blocks (see below). If there are no more observations, go to 6; otherwise, go to 5.
6. End of program.

To update the normals, let $(c1, c2)$, $(g1, g2)$, $(r1, r2)$ be the (first, last) columns of the current block corresponding to the set zero points, global parameters, and right-hand side. We should have $c1 > c2$ if the block does not contain any column for the set zero points, etc. Furthermore, let G_{ijg} and $\tilde{R}_g$ be the element of $\underline{G}_{ij}$ and column of $\underline{R}$, respectively, for the global parameter g (cf. Figure 1). The accumulation is then as follows:

```

for each star (i) in the batch
  for each set (j) in which the star was observed
    c = c(j) (the column for set j)
    if (c1 ≤ c ≤ c2) then
      add  $B_{ij}^2$  to element (c, c) ✓
      for each set (j') of the star
        if [c(j') ≤ c], add  $-\tilde{H}_{ij}^i \tilde{H}_{ij}$  to (c', c) ✓
      next j'
    endif
    for g = g1 to g2
      add  $B_{ij} G_{ijg} - \tilde{H}_{ij}^i \tilde{R}_g$  to (c, g) ✓
    next g
    for r = r1 to r2
      add  $B_{ij} h_{ij}$  to (c, r)
      for g' = nset+1 to nset+nglb
        add  $G_{ijg'} h_{ij}$  to (g', r)
      next g'
      add  $h_{ij}^2$  to (r, r)
    next r
  next j
  for g = g1 to g2
    for g' = nset+1 to g
      add  $-\tilde{R}_{g-g'}^i \tilde{R}_{g-g'} + \sum_j G_{ijg} G_{ijg'}$  ✓
    next g'
  next g
next i

```

6. Logical structure of SOLV23

In comparison with ACCU23, the solution program is very simple and straightforward. Apart from the Cholesky reduction/back-substitution, which is handled by the subroutine NEQSOL, the program should only provide the 'fixing' of 3 or 6 set zero points (depending on whether proper motions are included or not), set up the orthogonal null space vectors, and, after solution of the fixed normals, project the solution into the complementary space (NDAC/LO/018, 021, 032).

The first problem is to select the sets to be 'fixed'. If NASPAR = 2 or 3 (positions only, or positions and parallaxes), we should choose three sets with RGC poles as much as possible orthogonal to each other. As shown in NDAC/LO/021 (Figure 1), this can be done within a relatively short time interval of 1-2 months. However, we may want to avoid choosing sets with relatively small weight in the PRS solution. The weight of a set can be estimated roughly as proportional to the corresponding diagonal element of the normals before fixing. Now suppose we want to choose three RGC poles from a given interval of the order of 2 months. If we eliminate, say, the 50% sets with weight below median, we have some 60 points to choose from. There are consequently $(60 \cdot 59 \cdot 58) / (1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3) = 34,220$ possible ways of choosing the three points. It will be a simple matter to test each of these possibilities in order to select the best. A possible criterion for 'orthogonality' is simply the determinant of the three unit vectors to the RGC poles; its maximum absolute value = 1 is clearly reached only for orthogonal vectors. An alternative would be to assign each vector a length proportional to the weight of the set, and again use the determinant criterion. (Calculating 34,220 determinants and finding the maximum requires of the order of 10^6 arithmetic operations, or some 20 s on HP9000.)

For the full problem including proper motions (NASPAR = 5), it is necessary to fix six sets. This can be done by choosing three sets near the beginning of the observation interval and three near the end. There is no requirement on the relative orientation of the two vector triads.

To inspect the diagonal elements of the set zero points also serves another purpose, namely that of detecting any set without observations (diagonal = $\emptyset\emptyset$). Rather than modifying the block structure, such unknowns are simply rendered harmless by setting the diagonal element = $1D\emptyset$ (or any positive number) and disregarding the corresponding solution element (which in any case is = $\emptyset D\emptyset$).

Fixation is achieved by multiplying the three or six chosen diagonal elements by a large factor ($> 10^6$).

The null space vectors are stored in the last block, together with the rhs. This requires a minimum block length of $1 + \text{NCOL} + 6 * \text{NSET}$, where NCOL is the number of columns including the rhs, but excluding the null vectors. Initially, these extra columns should simply contain the rectangular equatorial components of the RGC pole unit vectors ($\underline{N}'\underline{r}_j$), respectively multiplied by the centralized set time [$\underline{N}'\underline{r}_j(T_j - \text{TEPOCH})$]. The components $\underline{N}'\underline{r}_j$ are of course used in selecting the fixation points, as described above. The null vectors are then orthonormalized (modified Gram-Schmidt, see NDAC/LO/021). After conventional solution of the fixed normals, the rhs is modified by subtracting from it its projection on each of the null vectors.

7. Current software status

ACCU23: The greater part of the main program exists in a preliminary form. Subroutines for calculating and I/O of blocking data, I/O of normal blocks, input of STARTF and output to the log file, are in a reasonably final form and have been tested. Several more I/O routines, the MESH algorithm, and numerical subroutines (matrix manipulations, e.g. Cholesky operations on submatrices of W) remain to be written.

SOLV23: The main subroutine NEQSOL for Cholesky reduction and back-substitution of blocked normals has been completed and tested (including the correct handling of interruptions). Nothing of the main program or subroutines for the pseudosolution (fixing and projection) exists.

On the whole, I estimate that the software is about 50% completed.

= not used

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{P} & \underline{R} & \underline{s} \end{pmatrix} = \sum_j \underline{A}'_{ij} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{A}_{ij} & \underline{G}_{ij} & \underline{h}_{ij} \end{pmatrix}$$

FIGURE 1. Disposition of array W(,) for setting up Step 2/3 observation equations.